

Work in progress:

Searching for biased information? Informational strategies and algorithmic curation

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Abstract

Democratic elections need a well-informed public. With the media environment increasingly influenced by algorithms, science and society need new tools to evaluate such algorithmic influence. In this work in progress paper, we study search engine bias in the context of the German federal elections in 2021. We combine a representative survey ($N = 1,641$) focused on information strategies and large-scale automated retrieval of search results by agent-based testing (ABT; 293,474 searches with 2,498,764 search results) to introduce an audience-centered approach to algorithmic auditing. This approach allows us to study both how voters use search engines in the run-up to elections and the content of the results they are shown. Preliminary results point towards a strong influence of different information-seeking strategies (i.e., looking for specific party, candidate, or issue information, or more general election guidance) on the structural diversity of search results. We outline further analysis strategies based on our dataset to investigate potential effects of different individual pathways to information on the structural diversity of search results.

Keywords: elections, political information-seeking, algorithms, search engines, agent-based testing

Work In Progress: Searching for Biased Information? Informational Strategies and Algorithmic Curation

More than 20 years ago, Introna and Nissenbaum (2000, p. 169) argued that web search engines “systematically exclude (in some cases by design and in some, accidentally) certain sites and certain types of sites in favor of others”. While written when search engines had merely come out of their infancy, this assessment has only gained in relevance. With their global use today, search engine algorithms significantly shape democracies’ access to information countless times more than they did 20 years ago.

Despite their democratic relevance, most search engines do not grant insight into their algorithmic mechanics. Most prominently and likely due to economic protection against competitors, Google does not share filtering rules and decisions with either the public or policymakers. Yet, for transparency reasons and interest in unbiased information, both the public and policymakers are keen to know how search engine algorithms prefer certain websites over others and whether algorithmic curation distorts general conceptions of balanced coverage.

The influence of search engines’ algorithmic content curation is of particular importance to the political sphere. Well-informed citizens require unbiased information and diverse sources for adequate decisions (Van Aelst et al., 2017). This is especially true ahead of elections when voters have a particular need for information (Atkin, 1973).

Generally speaking, the use of search engines for political information is extensive yet diverse. In a representative survey of online users across seven different countries, 40% report using search engines for information about politics “often” or “very often”, and only 10% report that they never do so (Dutton et al., 2017, p. 41). Relatedly, a recent tracking study has also named search engines the most common pathway to news online (Möller et al., 2020). Yet,

search engine use varies. Individual differences pertain to use frequency, access mode, usage behavior, and personal relevance for opinion formation (Kulshrestha et al., 2017).

Search engines' increasing importance for shaping public opinion has spurred academic and public interest in the consequences of biased search results. This is further fueled by experiments with manipulated and heavily biased search engine rankings, finding that search engines may even affect outcomes of contested elections by swaying undecided voters (Epstein et al., 2017; Epstein & Robertson, 2015).

However, whether a bias is present or not—and what constitutes a bias in the first place—is a normative question. While research cannot answer what algorithmically curated searches should return, it can describe what they currently return and how this presumably reflects varying understandings of democratic information ideals (Helberger, 2019). To this end, some authors have dug into how such democratic normative ideals could look like (Bozdag & van den Hoven, 2015; Dommert & Verovšek, 2021). Others take on a perspective of what ought to be the output of informational gatekeepers in a digital media environment (Nechushtai & Lewis, 2019; Nielsen, 2016).

Another more empirical approach is to investigate whether users with comparable information needs (e.g., using the same search query) but following different search pathways (e.g., search engines, locations, devices, browser histories) receive comparable outputs (Kravets & Toepfl, 2021; Puschmann, 2019). In that, the need for “compelling baselines” (Bandy, 2021, p. 26) when studying search-engine biases was highlighted repeatedly.

To address this issue, algorithmic audits have followed a wide variety of strategies (Mittelstadt, 2016; for a comparison of different kinds of audits, see Kitchin, 2017 and Sandvig et al., 2014). Particularly for the context of politics and elections, audits have yielded a strong

stream of research in recent years (Hu et al., 2019; Kravets & Toepfl, 2021; Metaxa et al., 2019; Puschmann, 2019; Robertson, Jiang, et al., 2018; Robertson, Lazer, et al., 2018; Steiner et al., 2020; Unkel & Haim, 2021; Urman et al., 2021). These approaches look at search engine biases by analyzing the content of search engine results pages (SERPs), focusing on the structural diversity of search results, content diversity of linked target pages, or ideological orientation of sources. In most cases, this encompasses manually or automatically querying search engines with presumably election-related search terms. Related work also tries to make assessments of the meaning and measuring of search engine biases more comparable, for example, through a general search bias quantification framework as suggested by Kulshrestha et al. (2019). The authors propose a four-fold approach by splitting bias into input, output, ranking, and time-average bias from which various measures can be computed.

Recently, calls for more audience-driven approaches have become more pronounced (see, for example, Bandy, 2021; Mustafaraj et al., 2020; Thurman et al., 2019). Criticisms of previous investigations include the utilization of “queries chosen by researchers themselves, without any input from voters” (Mustafaraj et al., 2020, pp. 559–560). Another criticism of previous research is the focus on front-running candidates’ queries that overshadows other potential domains of relevant election information (e.g., information about parties, issues, etc.). A likewise focus on (comparably weak) personalization effects neglects other individual factors contributing to SERP variation and randomization (Urman et al., 2021).

In this ongoing research project, our goal is to fill this gap by offering an audience-driven approach to the algorithmic auditing of search engines. We aim to learn how voters use search engines before upcoming elections and how different users’ SERPs are. Therefore, we systematically compare SERPs across users’ search engine experiences. We focus on the

structural diversity of SERPs (i.e., the presence and share of different website hosts) affected by differing physical (i.e., device and location) and informational (i.e., information strategies) pathways. These individual reflections of algorithmic biases will serve as a baseline to cross-estimate the level of bias available to a given electorate.

In light of an upcoming election as a situation with high information demands, we thus ask:

RQ1: Which pathways and informational strategies do potential voters employ when using search engines in the run-up to elections?

RQ2: How do pathways of (a) specific devices and (b) geographical locations as well as (c) informational strategies affect the structural diversity of election-related SERPs?

Data and Method

To answer these research questions, we combine representative insights into search engine use among voters with a large-scale automated collection of SERPs.

Specifically, we first conducted a survey representative of the German electorate to investigate how respondents utilized Google to inform themselves during the run-up to the 2021 German Federal Election. We focused on Germany due to the unpredictable outcome of the 2021 election as no incumbent candidate campaigned, leaving voters with high informational demands. Google dominates the German search engine market with usage share estimations of more than 90% (*Search Engine Market Share Germany*, 2021). Second, we employed an agent-based testing approach (Haim, 2020). Following the surveyed search engine pathways and information strategies, we emulated search engine user behavior to collect a wide variety of SERPs delivered to different devices, geographic locations, and information strategies.

The user perspective: representative survey

The survey was carried out online from Aug. 30th to Sep. 6th, 2021. This ensured temporal proximity to the election (Sep. 26th) while still giving us two weeks to run the ABT. Participants were recruited through YouGov, ensuring representativeness regarding age, gender, state, and formal education.

A total of $N = 1641$ participants (49% female, 51% male, $M_{\text{age}} = 50.3$ years, $SD_{\text{age}} = 17.6$, age range: 18-92 years) were surveyed on their political orientation, voting intentions, and usage of search engines before the election. Respondents' education was split evenly among the three major formal qualifications (2% still in school or no degree, 34% Mittelschule, 31% Realschule, 33% Abitur).

Most importantly, each respondent was asked to provide three search queries they would use to inform themselves about the upcoming election. For the first of these queries, no further instructions or limitations were provided (open-ended queries). For the other two queries, respondents were asked in relation to one issue drawn randomly out of 11 election-related societal issues (e.g., social security, immigration). This was to ensure a broad thematic spectrum of queries.

The content perspective: agent-based testing

We applied agent-based testing (Haim, 2020) using the ScrapeBot software (Haim, 2019) to orchestrate automated Google searches. With the search terms derived from the information strategies (RQ1, see below), automated searches were initiated every few minutes for two weeks before the election. For every search, the ScrapeBot opens a new browser window without any cookies or prior browsing history, visits google.de, randomly picks one of the respective queries, stores the results from the first result page, and closes the browser.

In total, 293,474 searches were performed, compiling a total number of 2,498,764 individual organic search results. Searches were orchestrated from a total of 32 servers, two in each of the 16 German states. One server always emulated a mobile device while the other emulated a desktop device.

To address the structural diversity of the search results, we first extract the host of each search result's URL. This procedure yielded 508 distinct hosts, with the top ten hosts accounting for one-third of all search results. All unique hosts are then manually coded by the authors into one of 8 mutually exclusive host categories, namely (1) general interest news, (2) special interest news, (3) government, (4) encyclopedia, (5) company, (6) private citizen, (7) social network site, (8) party/candidate.

Preliminary results and outlook

Information strategies

We employed cluster analysis of word embeddings to boil down surveyed queries into information strategies (RQ1). Pre-processing included filtering out meaningless answers and respondents who already cast their vote or showed no intention to do so, voters who do not rely on search engines for information, and answers that were too unspecific or too specific. This left us with 3,074 queries, which were automatically clustered through the use of word embeddings. The derived clusters were further condensed manually by the authors into 71 distinct queries belonging to four information strategy groups (Figure 1). The first three groups mirror the Michigan model of voter choice (Campbell et al., 1960) in that they represent information strategies on parties, candidates, and issues, respectively. The fourth group of queries focuses on more general election information and guidance and was thus labeled 'election guidance'. Membership is not mutually exclusive, meaning that an original query as formulated by the

survey respondents can belong to more than one of the four groups if the wording of the query suggested more than one information strategy (e.g., querying for a party-issue combination). This procedure allows us to match each individual survey respondent to one or more information strategies (and its associated queries). Consequently, we can also examine sociodemographic (see Table 1) and other personal characteristics by information strategy.

Structural search result diversity by information strategy

For a preliminary analysis of structural search result diversity (RQ2), we focus on the dominant hosts across all searches by information strategy. Figure 2 shows the top ten hosts and their respective categories per information strategy in the two-week run-up to the election. Consistent with prior findings (Unkel & Haim, 2021), the most prominent hosts are the online encyclopedia *Wikipedia*, the most frequent host for two information strategies (party and candidate information), and one of the leading German public-service news sites, *tagesschau*. Apart from these two hosts, however, the composition of the four information strategies varies widely.

Party queries

Almost half of the respondents employ a party-oriented information strategy with their open-ended query. Thereby, people search for party names or combinations of party names with issues, candidates, or various (translated) keywords such as “goals” or “manifesto” (see Figure 1). General interest news websites make up for half of the top ten hosts; however, party-owned media also ranks among the most prominent hosts for said information strategy. Notably, not all parties are equally represented with their own websites, with only the social democrats (*SPD*), the socialist left (*Die Linke*), and the greens (*Die Grünen*) represented among the top ten hosts. As we included every party equally in our final queries and normalized frequencies to counteract

random fluctuation, this already hints that those campaigners might be doing a better job in getting their party seen in search engines than others.

Candidate queries

About twelve percent of survey respondents reported using this strategy. In doing so, they use candidate names as search terms. Also, “triell” (a major TV debate) or “chancellor candidates” are used (see Figure 1). Whereas we only find Facebook in the party query column, social networking sites, particularly Instagram and Twitter, become more apparent when searching for candidate-related queries. This finding hints at the potentially higher levels of personalization and emotion, thereby echoing previous findings on social media and news-media imagery during election campaigns (Haim & Jungblut, 2021). Half of the hosts in the category are news outlets. One of them, namely the *handelsblatt*, focuses on economic and financial news. This highlights the importance of this general topic for candidates as opposed to the voters in our survey who report that this is only of modest significance to them.

Issue queries

A quarter of respondents reported with their open-ended query to employ a strategy of googling for specific issue-related terms. Often combined with party names or simply the word “parties”, this leads to queries like “labor market parties” or “refugees” (see Figure 1).

For this information strategy, we find that voters are mainly confronted with governmental hosts. The German statistical office, the Federal Agency for Civic Education, and two hosts owned by the large southern state of Baden-Württemberg show up when applying this search strategy. We interpret this as a raised source credibility appointed by Google to these hosts.

Election guidance queries

With two-thirds, this is the strategy that voters follow the most in their open-ended queries. Very prominent in our survey responses was the search term “wahl-o-mat”, a self-assessment website matching the user with parties’ standpoints. Another prominent query in this strategy is the up-front question of “who should I vote for”.

The host that comes up here most frequently is the federal BpB, the organization running the “wahl-o-mat” while obtaining a “politically balanced stance” (*Erlass über die Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung*, 2001; translation by the authors). The ninth rank of the top ten list here is also governmental, namely the website of the Bundeswahlleiter, which is the office responsible for organizing the election. In between those two, there are mainly news outlets again. Presumably, this is due to news outlets serving orientation-providing articles with comparisons or summaries of party positions.

Applying our descriptive findings to our second research question, we argue that peoples’ information strategy makes a difference in what kind of hosts they find themselves confronted with. That said, very few hosts dominate Google’s first result page, with the top ten hosts accounting for about a third of all search results. While in line with similar research (Kawakami et al., 2020; Puschmann, 2019; Urman et al., 2021), particularly news hosts may subsume a large variety in viewpoints and sentiment. Conversely, the limited set of parties and candidates who were able to be part of these top hosts points to a strong influence from strategic communication in determining search engine information biases.

Discussion and Outlook

This work-in-progress project aims at shedding light on the interrelation between users’ pathways as well as information strategies applied to search engines on the one hand and the

search engine's algorithmic decisions on what hosts to include or exclude in search results on the other hand. While our preliminary findings have already shown that users with different information strategies see different hosts, these analyses barely scratch the surface of our research interests. Notably, we aim to provide three additional insights for the conference.

First, we will compare search results across devices. Google has recently announced that a more generic technology will replace a system geared explicitly towards mobile devices. This will influence its ranking algorithm, and therefore, we are interested in how the use of particular devices affects the selection of resulting hosts (Dieter, 2021; *Details on the Page Experience Update*, 2021).

Second, we will compare search results geographically. Kliman-Silver et al. (2015) have shown that location matters in search engine results. Therefore, we aim at quantifying this effect across the 16 German states in the context of a national election.

Third, we will operationalize and quantify the request for “compelling baselines” (Bandy, 2021, p. 26). In that, we will compare individual users' pathways and information strategies to quantify their effects on host selection and host diversity. That said, and given this format's work-in-progress stage, we are explicitly open to new ideas for what other baselines or normative ideals could be and how they could be tested with our data.

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Tables & Figures

Figure 1

Flowchart for query formulation and search strategy grouping

Table 1*Sociodemographic variables by search strategies*

Search strategy	Mean age	Standard deviation age	Minimum age	Maximum age	Share female	Share male
Party queries	46.1	17.8	18	89	46.9%	53.1%
Candidate queries	58.4	15.1	19	82	52.4%	47.6%
Issues queries	54.0	16.1	18	85	54.3%	45.7%
Election guidance queries	50.4	15.8	19	79	50.0%	50.0%

Note: Calculations based on 3074 query answers (see Figure 1).

Figure 2

Top 10 Hosts by Information Strategy

Note: Frequency axis was normalized over query, location, day, and device.